

Sexually Transmitted Infections in Teenage- A Peek into the Future through the Lens of Past

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Abstract:

Sexually Transmitted Infections in Teenage- “A Peek into the future through the lens of past”. Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are a loosely defined constellation of infections and syndromes that are epidemiologically heterogeneous, but all of which are almost always or at least often transmitted sexually. A significantly higher risk of STDs is associated with young individuals than older adults. Multiple sexual partners and unprotected sex are more common among teenagers. Teenage age group comprises 13-19 yrs. Annually, approximately 30 million episodes of STI/RTI occur in India.

STDs and HIV are the main causes of loss of healthy lives in the age group of 15–40 year males, almost ranging to 15%. If STDs are not adequately treated, they can lead to a variety of complications. Media and government programs have created awareness of HIV/AIDS, but people in developing countries like India are less aware of STDs other than HIV/AIDS. Sexually transmitted infections have multifaceted impact on an individual and its family; this impact becomes comparatively more significant if the individual is in his teens.

So it is essential to have an explicit idea about STI in teenage group to efficiently tackle the disease and its various implications. The present paper is an initiative to addresses the same and is first of its kind in this tertiary centre and perhaps in this region. Our aim through this study was to study the prevalence of various STI in teenage age group.

Keywords: Sexually transmitted infections, Teenagers, Jharkhand.

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Introduction

Our aim through this study was to study the prevalence of various STI in teenage age group reported in STI clinic of tertiary care centre of Jharkhand. [1,2] As this study would be first of this kind in this region, hence this study might be immensely helpful for government and administration to target and divulge the information, logistics, planning, programme and resources for their better and efficient utilisation. [3,4]

Materials and methods:

- Study Design- Retrospective observational study (data from the hospital register).
- Study Period- Jan 2019 TO Oct 2023.
- Study Place- STI clinic, Tertiary care Centre, Jharkhand.

- Inclusion Criteria- Male/Female Patient presented to STI clinic with.
 - Age between 13-19 years.
 - Diagnosed with STI for the 1st time.

Observations and results

Out of total 26811 perused cases, 2971(11.1%) belonged to the teenage group and satisfied the inclusion criteria. 9 cases of HIV in teenagers were found in STI clinic register data. Among these 9 peoples there were 6 males and 3 were females. Out of the total cases, females made 63.55% (1888 cases) with maximum cases of vaginal discharge (664 cases). Males were 36.45% (1083 cases) with maximum cases of candidal balanoposthitis (228 cases).

Teenage group were divided into 13-16 years (32.92%) and 17-19 years (67.08%) age groups.

Maximum number of cases in both categories were of vaginal discharge i.e. 217 cases in 13-16 years and 447 cases in 17-19 years.

All the cases in the STI clinic register in teenage group did have some sort of education. Hence these cases were divided into 4 sub-categories i.e. Less than matriculations (5.22%), Matriculations (47.12%), High school (43.82%), Graduation (3.84%).

Lower abdominal pain were the majority cases in Less than matriculations (23 cases) and High school (190 cases). In matriculations group, maximum cases were of vaginal discharge (485

cases). In graduation pursuing cases, syphilis had the maximum share (23 cases).

According to the occupation status, Student were 57.12%, Private job were 5.45%, Housewife were 13.5%, Others were 23.93%. Vaginal discharge made the maximum share in student, housewife and others. Gonorrhoea constitutes the maximum cases of private job.

Location wise, Mango region of Jamshedpur reported 996 cases, followed by Birsanagar (192 cases), Chaibasa (171 cases), Saraikela (169 cases), Bistupur and Kadma (159 cases).

Graph 1: STI cases

Table 1:

GENDER			
DISEASE	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
VAGINAL DISCHARGE	0	664	664
LOWER ABDOMINAL PAIN	0	356	356
GUD	102	169	271
CANDIDAL BALANOPOSTHITIS	228	0	228
SYPHILIS	123	97	220
GONORRHOEA	92	67	159
NODULAR SCABIES	138	0	138
HERPES PROGENITALIS	41	65	106
MOLLUSCUM CONTAGIOSUM	55	31	86
GENITAL WARTS	53	26	79
ANORECTAL DISCHARGE	33	26	59
PEDICULOSIS PUBIS	27	12	39
OTHERS	191	375	566
TOTAL	1083 (36.45%)	1888 (63.55%)	2971

Graph 2: HIV cases

Table 2:

AGE GROUPS			
DISEASE	13-16	17-19	TOTAL
VAGINAL DISCHARGE	217	447	664
LOWER ABDOMINAL PAIN	143	213	356
GUD	87	184	271
CANDIDAL BALANOPOSTHITIS	53	175	228
SYPHILIS	71	149	220
GONORRHOEA	27	132	159
NODULAR SCABIES	57	81	138
HERPES PROGENITALIS	28	78	106
MOLLUSCUM CONTAGIOSUM	31	55	86
GENITAL WARTS	22	57	79
ANORECTAL DISCHARGE	18	41	59
PEDICULOSIS PUBIS	11	28	39
OTHERS	213	353	566
TOTAL	978 (32.92%)	1993 (67.08%)	2971

Table 3:

EDUCATION STATUS					
DISEASE	LESS THAN MATRIC	MATRIC	HIGH SCHOOL	GRADUATION	TOTAL
VAGINAL DISCHARGE	12	485	163	4	664
LOWER ABDOMINAL PAIN	23	125	190	18	356
GUD	17	129	114	11	271
CANDIDAL BALANOPOSTHITIS	19	77	129	3	228
SYPHILIS	9	45	143	23	220
GONORRHOEA	2	89	63	5	159
NODULAR SCABIES	16	68	47	7	138
HERPES PROGENITALIS	2	59	40	5	106
MOLLUSCUM CONTAGIOSUM	3	27	52	4	86
GENITAL WARTS	7	21	49	2	79
ANORECTAL DISCHARGE	5	15	35	4	59
PEDICULOSIS PUBIS	3	17	17	2	39
OTHERS	37	243	260	26	566
TOTAL	155 (5.22%)	1400 (47.12%)	1302 (43.82%)	114 (3.84%)	2971

Table 4:

OCCUPATION STATUS					
DISEASE	STUDENT	PVT. JOB	HOUSEWIFE	OTHERS	TOTAL
VAGINAL DISCHARGE	398	12	82	172	664
LOWER ABDOMINAL PAIN	233	9	76	38	356
GUD	167	7	54	43	271
CANDIDAL BALANOPOSTHITIS	166	16	0	46	228
SYPHILIS	139	17	23	41	220
GONORRHOEA	72	23	16	48	159
NODULAR SCABIES	79	12	0	47	138
HERPES PROGENITALIS	40	8	6	52	106
MOLLUSCUM CONTAGIOSUM	33	7	23	23	86
GENITAL WARTS	13	5	29	32	79
ANORECTAL DISCHARGE	24	4	12	19	59
PEDICULOSIS PUBIS	17	0	13	9	39
OTHERS	316	42	67	141	566
TOTAL	1697 (57.12%)	162 (5.45%)	401 (13.5%)	711 (23.93%)	2971

Figure 3: MAP-1

Discussion & Conclusion

In this study, females outnumbered the males in a ratio of 1.74:1.[5] As the data was collected from the STI clinic of tertiary care centre, data represents the convergence of data not just from the Dermatology and venereology department but also from the OBGY department. [6,7]

Hence this data has an advantage of providing wholesome picture in reference to disease but has a disadvantage of decreased precision when Dermatology and Venereology department is concerned. [8]

While concluding it can be clearly said that this study being very first of its kind in this region

would initiate the ball rolling for studies in similar fields in future. Also it will work as stepping stone for further studies in STI and devising the policies targeting effectively the burden of STI after efficiently analysis. [9,10]

References

1. Barot, Jigna P; Solanki, Avanita D; Patel, Neela M; Modi, Khushboo R; Bodar, Miral B. A Retrospective Study of the Pattern of Sexually Transmitted Diseases in Teenagers Attending Sexually Transmitted Disease Clinic during a 7-Year Period at a Tertiary Care Centre. Indian Journal of Paediatric Dermatology

- 19(3): 220-223, Jul-Sep 2018. | DOI: 10.4103/ijpd.IJPD_100_17
2. Jagat Jyoti Amar Singh, Ipseeta Satpathy, B. Chandra Mohan Patnaik. Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) among Gen Y in India. *J. Med. Chem. Sci.*, 2023, 6(8) 1897-1908
 3. National guidelines on prevention treatment and control of STI/RTI. NACO; August 20 07.
 4. National STI/RTI control and prevention programme. NACP III NACO; 2012.
 5. Marfatia YS, Sharma A, Joshipura SP, Valia RG, Valia AR. Overview of sexually transmitted diseases IADVL Textbook of Dermatology. 2008; Vol. 593rd ed Mumbai Bhalani Publishing House:1766-78
 6. Aral S, Over M, Manhart L, Holmes KK, Jamison D, Evans D, Alleyne G, Jha P, Breman J, Measham A, et al Sexually transmitted infections Disease Control Priorities in Developing Countries. 2006 Washington, D.C World Bank and Oxford University Press:311-30
 7. Narayanan B. A retrospective study of the pattern of sexually transmitted diseases during a ten-year period. *Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol* 2005;71:333-337
 8. Chugh TD, Gaiind R. Sexually transmitted infections. *Clin Lab Med.* 2012 Jun;32(2):143-58. doi: 10.1016/j.cll.2012.04.015. PMID: 22 726996.
 9. Forhan SE, Gottlieb SL, Sternberg MR, Xu F, Datta SD, McQuillan GM, Berman SM, Markowitz LE. Prevalence of sexually transmitted infections among female adolescents aged 14 to 19 in the United States. *Pediatrics.* 2009 Dec;124(6):1505-12. doi: 10. 1542/ peds.2009-0674. Epub 2009 Nov 23. PMID: 19933728.
 10. Shafii T, Burstein GR. An overview of sexually transmitted infections among adolescents *Adolesc Med Clin.* 2004;15:201-14.